

Second Focus Group

Research: Good evening everyone, my name is Research. Together with my friend Research 2, we are conducting a study/research aimed at understanding the opinions of JavaScript and TypeScript developers, especially those working in the industry with experience in unit testing, with Jest or any other library, since they all have the same tools.

Research: So, here's how the process will go: today, I'll provide a little context about the objective of the research, the overall goal we're aiming for. After that, I'll show images with code examples and leave you all open to discuss your thoughts and opinions on the specific code snippets and the questions posed. Let's move on.

Research: Our research consists of objectives, which are what we aim to achieve from this study, along with some code examples. We chose this research style because we could have opted for a form-based model with code examples, but in our objective, which aligns with our methodology, we tend to choose a focus group, which is generally a meeting like the one we're having now. We're gathering people from various areas, such as backend developers, frontend developers, etc., with different levels of experience, in order to see what each person can contribute based on what was presented.

Research: In general, the objectives are to understand the relevance of identifying bad practices in JavaScript/TypeScript test code and to gather feedback and views from developers—meaning you, the participants—on what is shown. From there, we will conclude whether our research has any positive or negative impact and what we can improve. Let's go for it...

Research: So, how will this work? I'll give you about 4 to 5 minutes to analyze the example. In this case, we'll always have the title as

defined in the literature. Doctors and researchers define this title, and on the right, we have the code example. On the left, we have a question trying to provide context. Feel free to ask any questions, "I didn't understand the question, could you give another example?" or "Can you contextualize it?" Feel free to ask.

Research: Here's the process: I will read the question, and you'll have some time to analyze the code and ask any questions about the question or context. Feel free to ask.

Research: Initially, we have the "test without description." Think of a scenario in your work context. You are working, either implementing or maintaining an existing test, and you come across a test file that contains several examples of code like the one here, where there's a test block, and in this block, we have the test itself, which has a peculiar factor—the absence of a descriptive text. Consider that your test case doesn't have the descriptive text. How does this problem affect the readability and understanding of the test case? In other words, take some time to analyze, and let me know your opinions. If you came across this in your work, would it have a positive or negative impact, or is there something you think you could learn from this? You have about 4 minutes for this discussion, folks.

P4: Can I speak now, Research?

Research: Feel free to speak, if someone else agrees or disagrees with you, they can chime in. It's about generating this discussion between devs and reaching a general conclusion.

P4: From my perspective, it negatively impacts the situation because the code, or rather the test, doesn't explain what it's testing. So I don't know the real functionality, and I can't understand it from the test

itself. Also, if the test fails, in the logs, I won't be able to identify where the test failed. That's basically it.

Research: Does anyone else have an opinion? Do you agree with P4?

P6: I agree. I don't see any positives in creating a test without a description. It just increases the workload of checking the function to figure out what the function is testing. So, yeah, just a negative point.

P5: I also agree.

Research: Does anyone else want to speak? Feel free. If no one else is speaking, I'll ask a question. Have you ever come across a similar situation when you were working...?

P6: No, not in my case.

P7: Not for me either. We log it in the console as "error"...

Research: Alright.

P9: I think the most common case is tests with poorly written descriptions...

Research: Got it, moving on. Let's go to the next one.

Research: Now, we have a case related to what P9 just mentioned. It's called the Anonymous Test, and in this case, we have the presence of a descriptive text. However, how does the absence of a clear description impact the readability and understanding of a test case? So, looking at this code snippet, or any other context you might face, if I'm writing a test for a user class and there's a description that doesn't make sense, does that impact it in any way?

P6: I see this one as pretty much the same, or maybe even worse than the last one, because the description isn't helping at all. And even if someone else reads it, since it's such a vague description, they might

think it's one thing when it's actually something else. Not in this example because it literally says nothing, but if the description is too vague, the dev might think it's doing one thing but it could actually be doing something else. So, I think this could be even more destructive than the previous example.

Research: Any other thoughts?

P8: I also don't see any positive aspect. Depending on the context, it's useful to separate blocks and the functions should throw errors, but there's a need for a description of what kind of error will be thrown. But I can't see any positives with these two words (in the test description).

Research: Alright, anyone else? Do you agree with your colleagues?

P9: The point I see is that the lack of a clear description makes the developer... In repetitive tests, because there's no clarity in the test, they might end up testing something more than once due to lack of clarity.

Research: Anyone else? Can we move forward? Since no one else has anything to add, let's proceed. Afterward, we can do an overview.

Research: Here's another example, a very specific case where you are using any kind of logs in your tests. So, the Transcribing Test is basically when we end up using console logs. Looking at this flow, do you identify any problems? Does it impact readability, clarity, and relevance? If you have another example, not necessarily this one, just imagine another case or context where you're adding logs to your tests.

P6: I think logs in tests can have some usefulness. Personally, I don't mind seeing them; my eyes automatically ignore them. But I'm not a big fan. If you're going to write something you're doing, I'd prefer it be done using variable names or function calls, rather than logs. But if

there's a log with some kind of information, I personally don't mind. I'm not a fan of it, but I don't mind.

Research: Alright, do you see anything else? Any other colleagues?

P5: I have a similar opinion. I think it's fine to use `console.log` when you're testing and building something, especially when you're changing something in the test. But I follow the same line as P6 in that I don't really care. It's pretty indifferent to me whether there's a `console.log` or not. It's more useful when you're updating something in the test or when you deliberately make a test fail first to later fix it. So for me, it's kind of indifferent; it neither helps nor hinders. It's more helpful when you're testing and creating the test.

Research: Alright, anyone else?

P4: Yeah, I think logs in tests help when you're trying to debug something in the test or an error, and you need to debug it. But in the final version of the test, I'd prefer not to have logs. If the log is trying to describe something in the test, that should be handled by the test's description itself. If you need it, maybe the test is too big, and you should break it down because it's become too complex, and that's why you need a log to explain part of it.

Research: Got it, anyone else? Did anyone see something that another colleague missed?

P8: I'm not sure if I should add this, but I think when you use `console.log` this way, which I also don't think is ideal, it might indicate issues in the code when you're testing. If you need a `console.log` to understand an error message that should have been broken down somewhere but isn't clear, that's an issue.

Research: Alright, is everyone okay with this?

P9: One final point. I agree with the majority. In some cases, it doesn't bother me, especially when we're testing something specific or debugging. But, if we're using logs in unit tests, we're violating one of the core principles of unit testing, which is interacting with the external environment by redirecting strings to the user's console output. It doesn't pose a performance issue, but it does go against good practices, especially in unit testing. But honestly, I feel indifferent in this regard.

Research: Alright, anyone else? Any opinion? Anything you saw that another colleague didn't? If not, we can move on to the next example.

Research: At some point, you'll be maintaining a codebase or implementing a new test, and you'll likely come across commented-out code. In this case, specifically, we have the Comments Only Test. The goal here is to understand the impact of having a completely commented-out test. In this example, it's fully commented out. There's no executable code. How does this impact your test code or your understanding as a developer? Do you see any impact, or do you think it doesn't affect you, or is the presence of a fully commented-out test relevant?

P5: For me, it depends on the size of the commented-out test. If it's this small, I understand it's something you can just delete and rewrite because it's just a comment, and it doesn't help at all. Now, if it's a big test, and for some reason, no one could make it work, so they left it commented out—if it's too big, you'll have to scroll through the file, which makes it harder to navigate within the file. It's basically dead code, probably not helping anything, unless it has a reason for being there. If it's commented out, that reason should also be inside the comment. Otherwise, it's just code that, in my opinion, doesn't help at all—it doesn't do anything and just causes more trouble than it's worth because it's not doing anything.

Research: Any more colleagues?

P8: I see this as, of course, I also agree with José that it can hinder the visibility of the code. But the only useful case for this would be if it was a feature you had in the project that didn't work, or if you had to roll back and instead of rewriting all the code, you left it there or created a new branch. That would be ideal. But I think that would be somewhat useful. Other than that, I don't see any positive points.

P6: For me, from my own experience, commented-out code rarely gets uncommented. So, in my opinion, if it was a feature we removed, as P8 said, and it's no longer going to be used, just delete the entire code, delete the entire feature. If, someday, we want to revisit it, we have version control tools, and if we maintain good commit practices, we can check and go back. I think it only hinders the developer. There's no need to keep anything commented out.

P8: Yes, definitely. Creating a separate branch would be the ideal way to handle it.

Research: Anyone else?

P4: I agree with what everyone has said. And I think that in this case, for example, since the test is completely commented out, there's no comment explaining why, right? If there was a comment explaining why, even though it would still be bad, at least we'd know why it was commented out. Maybe the build broke, or it was a critical bug update, and someone had to comment out the test to pass the build. That happens. A comment would at least explain why the test was commented out and would be fixed later. So, even though it's bad to have a commented-out test with an explanation, this case is worse because there's no clue as to why it was commented out. We don't

know if it's code that should have been removed or if it was an urgent situation.

Research: Got it, anyone else want to speak up? Or found something that others didn't catch? Are you all satisfied? Are you sure? Do you agree with others or disagree?

P7: I agree with what they said. I mean, if you set up your branching structure correctly, there's no need to save that code. Just create a new branch, leave it there if you need to come back to it later, or maybe just keep the three lines of code. But yeah, in our example, it was a bigger piece of code.

Research: But everyone agrees? Great, we can move on. No one else spoke up, so let's continue.

Research: In the other case, we had a fully commented-out test. In this case, it's practically the same idea, but instead of being fully commented, it has multiple comments. Not necessarily the same as this example here, which describes maintenance, but do you think the presence of so many comments would have any negative or positive impact? If there were more than this, would it affect the test in any way?

P5: I think comments generally need a good reason to be there. Because usually when you see a comment, you end up reading it, and in this case, they're all redundant. They literally repeat what the next line is going to do, and the line itself already says that. Sometimes you find a line that you don't understand, and that's when a comment makes sense, especially for more complex things. But in this case, I'd rather not have them because the next lines already explain what's going to happen. If it were a more complex code, like some complicated calculation, then it'd make sense to have a comment explaining it. But here, it's just redundancy, so it's better to remove it since it's not adding anything—just extra text.

Research: Perfect. Just a note, it doesn't necessarily need to be the exact case here, but when you come across something like this, with many comments, regardless of what the comments are saying, how does that impact you? Feel free to continue with your thoughts.

P8: I also think it's unnecessary, not just in this example. The right approach would be to have explanatory code with well-named variables and functions. The only case where such comments would make sense would be for didactic purposes, like for people learning in a controlled environment. Outside of that, in code that's going to be maintained, it's unnecessary.

P4: I agree with what everyone said. It makes the test harder to read, more verbose. Also, when this test is changed, one thing I've seen happen is that the code is altered, but the test remains the same, and sometimes the comment, even if it was made with good intentions or made sense at the time, isn't updated. So, the comment loses its meaning. It becomes a comment for old code, and that just makes things worse.

Research: Anyone else? Do you agree, disagree? Did you notice something that others missed? If no one else wants to speak, we can move on.

Alright, now we're going to look at another test case, where we use methods like `ToString`. In this case, we're using the `ToString` method to compare primitive types and data structures in the test. So, you can analyze this context here. I don't know if you've encountered this in your work context, where someone is using `ToString` in a test. If you have, please share your opinion on how it went, what the `ToString` method was used for. Based on this code, do you see any problems with it or any other context where you've observed the use of `ToString` in test cases? Do you think using `ToString` impacts

the clarity, reliability, or results of the test? Or does it have another impact?

Research: Do you have more colleagues?

P8: I see this as, of course, I also agree with José that this can mess with the code's readability, but the only useful purpose for this would be a feature that you had in the project and couldn't get it to work, or you had to roll back, and instead of rewriting the entire code, you leave it there, or create a new branch. That would be ideal. But I think that would be somewhat useful. Apart from that, I can't see any positive point.

P6: For me, I think commented-out code is rarely revisited and you only come back to uncomment the code, right? So, for me, in my opinion, if the test was as P8 said, if it was a functionality we removed and aren't going to use anymore, delete all the code, delete the entire functionality, and if one day we want to do the same thing again, we have version control tools that we can check and keep good commit standards per PR, you can always go back and see it. I think it just gets in the way of the dev. I think there's no need to keep anything commented-out at all.

P8: Yes, definitely. Creating a separate branch would be ideal.

Research: Anyone else?

P4: I agree, I think with what everyone said, and especially in this case, for example, it's a comment, actually the test is fully commented-out, and there are no comments explaining why, right? If there was a comment saying why, it would still be bad, but if there was at least a comment, we would know why it was commented out, right? Maybe the build broke, it was a critical bug update, someone had to comment out a test to pass the build, that could happen, and

then at least a comment would explain why the test was commented out and would be fixed later. This is already bad with the explanation in the comment, and the case as it is, even worse. Because, well, no one knows why the test was commented out, doesn't know if it's code that should've been removed, if it was an emergency, anyway.

Research: Alright, anyone else want to speak up? Or found something that others didn't notice? Are you all sure this is it, do you agree with each other, or disagree?

P7: I agree with what they said because, man, if you create a proper branch structure, there's no need to save this code. Just create a new branch and leave it there, forgotten. If you need to go back, you can search for it. Or, I don't know, just three lines of code and it's done, but it could be a bigger piece of code, as a colleague mentioned, right? But this is just our example here.

Research: So, everyone agrees, that's fine, we can move on. Alright. No one else spoke up, let's proceed to the next example.

Research: In the other case, we had a completely commented-out test. In this case, it's almost the same concept, but instead of the test being fully commented out, it will have several comments. Not necessarily the example you can analyze has to have comments like this one, which are somewhat describing maintenance, or do you think the presence of many comments here is an example? But if there were more than this, would it have any negative or positive impact?

P5: I think comments generally have to have a good reason to be there because usually when you see a comment, you end up reading it, sometimes, and in this case, all of them are redundant, they're literally saying what the next line will do, and the line itself is saying it. Sometimes you find a line that you don't understand anything about, and then it really makes sense to add a comment when it's something more complex. But in this case, basically, I'd prefer if there weren't

any because the next lines already explain what will happen. Now, if it was much more complex code, if it were some crazy calculation that needs to be done, then add the comment, explain, and it helps. But in this case, it's just redundancy, so it's better to remove it since it's not adding anything, just text.

Research: Perfect. Just a note, right, it doesn't necessarily have to be just the case here, right, but when you encounter an example like this, regardless of what the comment is saying, if you encounter many comments, what impact does that have for you? Feel free to continue with the next ones.

P8: I also think it's unnecessary, not just in this example, but the right path would be to have explanatory code with variable names and function names. The only case for using comments like this would be for didactic purposes for people learning in a closed environment. Apart from that, in code that will undergo maintenance, no one needs that.

P4: I agree with what everyone has already said. I think it hinders the readability of the test, makes it more verbose, more text to read, and also when this test is altered, one thing that I see happening is that the code is changed, but the test remains the same, and sometimes the comment, even if it was well-intentioned in a scenario that made sense, the comment is usually not updated. So, it loses its meaning. It comes with a comment from old code, and then, well, it makes it worse.

Research: Anyone else? Do you agree or disagree? Did you notice something that the other colleague didn't? Ready, since no one has spoken up until now, we can proceed.

Research: Alright. Now, we're going to move on to another test case, which is when we use methods like `ToString`. In this case, we are using the `ToString` method to compare primitive types and data

structures in the test. So, you can analyze this context here. I'm not sure if you've encountered a situation in your work context where someone used `toString` in a test case. If so, feel free to share how it went. Based on what's written in this code, do you find any issues with it, or any other context where the use of `toString` in a test case may be problematic? And do you think the presence of the `toString` method impacts the clarity, reliability of this test, or does it cause another impact?

P6: I think there might be cases where `toString` could be used, but I can't think of any right now, and it affects both readability, since it's an extra method to read, and the test's effectiveness. For example, if `getUser` returns an age as a number, and for some reason, your code breaks and returns a string instead, it won't catch that error, you know? So, it could be that you're... I'm not sure if it's possible to call `toString` within a string, but either way, I think it's just an extra step, another thing to do that won't help at all, neither with readability nor the test's effectiveness.

Research: Got it, perfect. Any other colleague agree, disagree?

P5: I agree, and I think especially with JavaScript, and not TypeScript, if for some reason `getUser` returns, well, this would cause the test to fail since it wouldn't match, but the error wouldn't be related to the functionality, it would be related to how the test is written. What ends up hurting the reliability of the test is that the error occurs, but not for the right reasons or in the right way, and this can sometimes confuse things. In this example, it's simple, but if we start thinking about something more robust, it could lead to something more complex and harder to understand.

Research: Got it, is that it? Any other colleagues see something that others didn't? Do you agree with the opinion? Disagree? Have you used it?

P4: I can't think of any scenario where it would be useful to do that, especially in JavaScript. The only scenario I thought of would be if you had to compare objects, two different instances of the same object, but there are already methods for that, at least in Jest, it has built-in functions to handle those cases. Comparing objects that are not necessarily the same instance. But for that, I didn't see any scenario where it would be necessary to use `toString`. And I think it gets in the way. It makes the test more verbose.

Research: Any other colleagues? Any opinions on that? So, since no one else has spoken, we can proceed. I think this is the last example, right? Then, we'll do a quick overview. This case is more focused on fixtures. I don't know if you're familiar with the term fixture, right? But basically, FIX is the term for saying that data has been mocked, right? So, when you're mocking your test, you mock the data and validate your test that way. So, here we have an example of code on the right with the mocks used. What are the risks associated with using general fixtures in test cases, and how can this impact the reliability and independence of the tests? Looking at this scenario here, do you see any problems or anything peculiar, even in relation to the code itself? Feel free to share.

P6: I'm really against testing mocked data because, as you can see, it's not testing anything. You can change anything in your database, and it will still work unless you change the `user`, `admin`, or `guest` class. But, it's not really testing anything, and that's a bit dangerous because if you change something in your code, due to your test being mocked, you might forget to change your mocks.

Research: Did you notice anything else in reference to the code?

P5: I agree with P6, especially in rare exceptions. I think there are really few exceptions where mocked data makes sense. Generally, I think of situations where you have a controller that needs to do something, and you want to know if that controller's functionality is working. Not something simpler like a CRUD, but maybe you need to perform some calculation, and then you mock the data to always ensure the controller is returning it correctly. But apart from that, I can't think of any other reason. Personally, I also don't like mocks. It feels like I'm not testing anything since I'm setting what's going to come, so I can't have any unpredictability because everything is within what I'm already expecting..

Research: Ready. Do the other colleagues agree, or did they notice something that others didn't? Looking from line 1 to 14 here, is there something peculiar that you didn't catch? What did you observe? And when we're talking about mocks, are you sure about this?

P4: I think that specifically in this case, in this file, in this example, besides what was already mentioned, there's another issue with this code. If another test modifies some mock data, it will end up impacting another one. The question is about the independence between tests, right? So, if there's a case where a test changes some mock data, it could impact another test.

Research: Alright. Anyone else? Do you agree with P4? Did you notice something the others missed? Or not?

P6: I think, just guessing here, if a test changes something, it wouldn't affect the others because the **Before Each** runs before every test, so it will always reset before each test.

P4: True, I hadn't noticed the **Before Each** there.

Research: And would this affect anything in terms of performance? Do you think it would impact anything else?

P5: Well, imagining that it's something like an insertion in a data block... Imagine that you start having more types of users and adding more tests. Every time, for each test, you'd be creating new users, new admins, new guests, new moderators... And then it starts to scale, and you have a lot of work within each test. That definitely impacts performance in some way.

P9: Research, when you talk about general mocked data in test cases, are you referring to unit tests or other types of tests, like integration tests or tests in QA?

Research: In this specific case, we're focusing more on unit tests.

P9: Well, in unit tests, from my point of view, it's highly recommended to use mocks. Because when you're testing a unit of code, you're testing the smallest functionality within your code. For example, if you want to test how a function behaves. In this sense, it doesn't matter much if you make a request to the database, an API, or an external gateway, because what you want to test is purely the behavior of your function. So, in this case, the mock makes sense. Another point I want to mention is that you need to recreate mocks with every interaction. In this case, there's no **describe**, but when I write the **before**, it runs before each test in **describe**, which ensures no test interferes with another. So, if you remove the test from line 12, the one from line 9 will still work perfectly. It's only the **before each** that ensures this. But these are the points I wanted to mention.

Research: Got it.

P4: There's also a point in this example where there's a mock for the guest, but it's not used in the tests. Its non-use...

Research: Do you think that would impact anything?

P4: Well, it's a piece of unused code, and it's useless; anyway, it gets in the way. Unnecessary code always causes problems. It can also hinder maintenance. Sometimes, it can be confusing—there's data there that's not being used, etc.

Research: Do the others agree with P4? Any differing opinions?

P8: I agree. The code shouldn't call a **before each** for every test with something that won't be used in each test, or at least in most of the tests. I also strongly agree with what Almeirindo said about mocks being really useful for unit testing. The important thing is to test the integration. And I think that's it.

Research: Alright. Anyone else? If no one has anything else to add, we can do a quick overview. Anyone disagree, agree, or notice something else? Since no one spoke up, I think we can wrap up here, and then I'll give you a full overview.